

D6.1 Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication Activities V1

Deliverable 6.1

Grant Agreement n°. 101084234

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VERSION HISTORY

Ver.	Date	Comments/Changes	Author/Reviewer
0.1	01/06/2023	First draft	CE
0.2	09/06/2023	Draft reviewed by consortium members	Anastasia Oprea, Annie Roos
0.3	26/06/2023	Draft reviewed by Project Coordinators	Maura Farrell and Louise Weir
1	29/06/2023	Final version	Víctor Ricardo Martínez, Elena Herrera, Michelle Perello, Beatrice Avagnina, Marlene Santacruz

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

Project Acronym	FLIARA	
Project Title	FLIARA: Female-Led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas	
Type of action	HORIZON-RIA	
Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2022-COMMUNITIES-01-01	
Project Start Date	01/01/2023	
Project Duration	36 months	
Work Package	WP6 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation	
Deliverable	D6.1 Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities – V1	
Due Date	30/06/2023	
Submission Date	29/06/2023	
Dissemination Level ¹	PU	
Deliverable Responsible	Consulta Europa	
Version	1	
Status	First version of a living document	
Author(s)	Marlene Santacruz, Víctor Ricardo Martínez, Elena Herrera, Michelle Perello, Beatrice Avagnina	CE
Reviewer(s)	Anastasia Oprea, Annie Roos, Maura Farrell, Louise Weir	ECOLISE, LNU, GALWAY

¹ PU= Public, SEN= Sensitive.

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ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS

PC	Project Coordinator
CD&E	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
D	Deliverable
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	General Assembly
WP	Work Package
Project partners	
Galway	NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY
TU Delft	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT
TEAGASC	TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY
UNICAL	UNIVERSITA DELLA CALABRIA
LWL	LONGFORD WOMEN S LINK CLG
UTU	TURUN YLIOPISTO
UL	UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI
CE	CONSULTA EUROPA PROJECTS AND INNOVATION SL
HNEE	HOCHSCHULE FUR NACHHALTIGE ENTWICKLUNG EBERSWALDE
ELARD	ASSOCIATION EUROPEENNE LEADER POURLE DEVELOPPEMENT RURAL
UOULU	OULUN YLIOPISTO
ECOLISE	RESEAU EUROPEEN POUR DES INITIATIVES COMMUNAUTAIRES SUR LES CHANGEMENTS CLIMATIQUES ET LE DEVELOPPEMENT DURABLE
MENDELU	MENDELOVA UNIVERZITA V BRNE
LNU	LINNEUNIVERSITETET
HLK	HOGSKOLAN FOR LARANDE OCH KOMMUNIKATION I JONKOPING - HLK SCHOOL OF EDUCATION AND COMMUNICATION

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Plan serves as a comprehensive guide for the project's communication and dissemination activities, as well as the exploitation activities that will be internally updated as required. The document outlines the core activities to be implemented during the first 18 months of the project, emphasising the FLIARA exploitation activities, tools, procedures, and guidelines that partners will adhere to in order to achieve clear, consistent, and coherent communication and dissemination of project results to the target audiences.

The Plan encompasses both internal and external communication, defining the communication targets to be reached, the appropriate communication tools to be employed, and the monitoring and reporting mechanisms for communication activities. Furthermore, it includes an exploitation roadmap and highlights opportunities for maximising the project's impact and outcomes. The plan establishes the responsibilities of the project and its consortium and provides detailed guidelines for implementing a variety of dissemination and communication activities. The present plan will be regularly reviewed and updated to adapt to evolving needs and optimise the impact and sustainability of the project's outcomes.

1. CONTEXT ANALYSIS

1.1 THE PROJECT

FLIARA (Female-Led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas) is an innovative project that will employ a transdisciplinary methodology to improve understanding, awareness, and recognition of women's role in a more sustainable rural future.

The project aims to provide a more effective innovation ecosystem that spotlights women's achievements, inspires, and shares knowledge, connects them with key innovation actors, and increases their visibility within national and international decision-making contexts. The FLIARA project demonstrates the innovative capacity of women in farming and in rural areas, with a particular focus on all four dimensions of sustainability (environmental, economic, social, and cultural). To achieve this, partners of the project will investigate women-led innovations on farms and in wider rural areas through a thematic case-study approach, examining their pathways in the innovation ecosystem.

FLIARA will develop proposals for how more effective policy and governance frameworks can support women's capacity to contribute to the sustainability of rural areas.

1.2. THE CONSORTIUM

The FLIARA project is coordinated by University of Galway and it has a consortium of 15 partners from 10 different countries, ranging from universities (University of Galway, TU Delft, HLK - Jönköping, UNICAL, UTU, UL, HNEE, UOULU, MENDELU, and LNU) and European Networks (ELARD, ECOLISE), to a SME (CE), a Community Organisation and Social Enterprise (LWL) and a national agricultural state agency and extension advisory body (Teagasc) that are engaged with female-led innovation in rural and farming areas. The multi-disciplinary consortium has been designed to ensure that the project objectives are met and that the call topic is addressed effectively.

1.3. FLIARA'S DISSEMINATION WORK PACKAGE

Work Package 6 (WP6) – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation aims to:

- Develop the CD&E Strategy identifying the most pertinent CD&E activities, channels, target groups and tools required;
- Design and initiate a visibility campaign highlighting existing women-led innovations in farming and rural areas;
- Establish synergies with other multi-actor local, national and EU networks and relevant EU-funded projects;
- Disseminate the project recommendations and outputs at regional, national and European level through novel, multimethod communication activities;
- Design and implement the exploitation strategy ensuring solutions generated are accessible and available to end-users;
- Deliver social media communications training to enhance the skills of women in farming and rural areas.

In this context, the FLIARA consortium recognises the importance of effective dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities to ensure the successful implementation and impact of the project.

1.4. DELIVERABLE 6.1

The success of the project relies not only on the quality of the research and innovation work, but also on the ability to communicate and disseminate findings effectively to relevant audiences. To ensure this, CE have developed, within D6.1, a comprehensive plan for dissemination and exploitation, including communication activities. The deliverable entails 6 sections:

Section 1 lays the foundation with a thorough Context Analysis of the project, followed by Section 2, which explores the Communication and Communication Approach. Within Section 3 the focus shifts to the Visibility Campaign. Section 4 delves into the Exploitation Plan and Opportunities and Section 5 provides a detailed overview of the Progress on WP6. Conclusions are contained within Section 6.

The WP6 leader, CE, will oversee the continuous revision and updating of the present deliverable to ensure a smooth and effective implementation throughout the project. The plan will be updated at M18 (D6.2) to reflect the evolving needs of the project. A final version of the strategies will be developed by the end of the project (D6.3) to ensure maximum impact and visibility of the project's results and its exploitation.

The involvement of all the project partners in the definition and improvement of the plan and, in general, in WP6 dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities will be fundamental. Coordinated and guided by WP6 Leader CE, the whole consortium will disseminate and communicate relevant information about the project to multiple audiences in a strategic, coherent, and effective manner and in accordance with the Grant Agreement.

2. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION APPROACH

The aim of the FLIARA plan for dissemination, communication, and exploitation is to ensure that the project message is effectively delivered to the target audiences and the action promotes stakeholder engagement and participation and that it enhances the overall visibility and understanding of the project.

Therefore, the approach will focus on ensuring that the FLIARA strategy under WP6 is centrally involved in influencing and promoting innovative women-led initiatives in farming and rural areas at everyday societal and policy levels by establishing, mobilising and exploiting interlinkages with existing multi-actor networks, EU-funded projects and other relevant initiatives supporting and promoting women-led innovations in farming and rural areas at regional, national and EU level.

2.1. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PRINCIPLES

A set of six principles have been established to orient FLIARA's communication and dissemination action, internally and externally:

- 🗨️ **Reliability.** Through WP6, FLIARA will promote high-quality research that makes use of sound methodology, design, analysis, and resource usage.
- 🗨️ **Tailoring of messages/usage of appropriate language.** FLIARA needs to be able to speak to a variety of actors and stakeholders with different backgrounds and objectives in mind. To achieve this, FLIARA will follow a multi-layered communication strategy that formulates core messages tailored to the needs and expectations of the various target audiences, and expressed in appropriate language (such as specialised, technical wording communication or simple and direct, jargon-free communication).
- 🗨️ **Exploitation of synergies.** FLIARA will maximise impact by exploiting efficiency opportunities of synergies at two levels - internally, between partners and WPs, and externally, namely with external networks, organisations that support and collaborate with the project and through platforms that have relevant remits and with other relevant EU-funded projects.
- 🗨️ **Gender sensitive communication.** In its communication, FLIARA will be conscious of gender sensitive and appropriate communication. For example, certain words and images can perpetuate images of socially prescribed gender roles and behaviours.
- 🗨️ **Disruptive.** As this is a project that is bringing a new perspective to the table the communication intends to be disruptive, innovative and breaking with old stigmas associated with gender in agriculture, farming and rural innovations.

2.2. TARGET GROUP IDENTIFICATION

As a starting point to plan communication and dissemination activities, the definition and identification of target groups relevant for the project is essential. Target groups are the key to reach a wide audience, as such different channels such as social media accounts, events, press release, website and open-access platforms will be employed to reach these target groups. FLIARA has identified the main target groups of the project: policy makers, innovation support services, scientific community, and civil society organisations and associations.

Based on these main target groups, the communication and dissemination channels and the type of information to be used throughout the project are summarised in the table below:

Table 1. Target groups identified.

Target Group	Communication & Dissemination Channels	Type of activity
Policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshops • Newsletter • Press releases • Fact sheets • Promotional materials • Forum • Events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community of practice • Policy design and assessment • Project results • Project description and updates • Policy abstract / brief • Advantages of the research
Innovation Support Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forum • Synergies • Workshops • Conference presentations • Open-access publications and journals • Scientific reviews • Trainings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foresight and trend analysis under WP2 • Innovative practices of women in rural areas • Women-Led innovations in farming • Community of practice network

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Media • Website • Promotional materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foresight and Trend analysis • Gender equality performance examination across four WP1, WP3, WP4 and WP5 • Project results
Scientific community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisation and participation of project's dedicated events • Scientific reviews • Specialised media • Factsheets • Social media • Final conference • Focus group • Workshops • Promotional materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Case studies • Trends and megatrends • Glossary of terms • Key findings • Innovations • Comparative analysis of innovative practices between countries • Project publications
Civil society (citizens) organisations and associations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media campaign • Social networks • Promotional materials • Project website • Focus groups • FLIARA Toolkit • Newsletter • Specialised Press and Media • Events • Trainings • Guide • Video blogs • Podcasts • Fact Sheets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project results • Spotlight of women-led innovation • Innovative practices • Innovation ambassadors • Interviews • Project description and updates • Project Publications

2.3. COMMUNICATION TOOLS

To engage with identified stakeholder groups during the project duration, WP6 activities rely on a range of essential tools. These tools include visual identity, promotional materials, website, which are described in the following sections.

2.3.1. VISUAL IDENTITY

One of the fundamental pillars for wide and efficient communication and dissemination of the results of the project is a strong visual identity. It will play a key role in raising awareness of the project.

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The logo has been created by the project coordinator's team at the proposal stage and Consulta Europa (CE) has adapted its visual identity for communication and dissemination purposes.

The female icons featured within the logo created by the University of Galway team essentially showcase that every woman, of every age, race, sexual orientation, profession (from researchers, to beekeepers to chefs to farmers) have a seat/place at FLIARA's 'table', where examples and ideas of innovation and innovative practices can be shared and co-created by all, through the multi-factor approach (i.e. represented through the lightbulb).

The predominant mulberry colour of the FLIARA logo, is inspired by the Mulberry tree. This tree symbolises 'Wisdom and Patience' as Mulberries do not bud until the danger of frost has passed, and so they symbolise patience. When they finally bud, however, mulberries bud so rapidly that they appear to have budded overnight, symbolising expediency and wisdom. For all these attributes, the Greeks actually linked the plant to the goddess of wisdom, Athena. This is quite apt in relation to what FLIARA is hoping to achieve, as women have been waiting far too long to 'bud', due to patriarchy, and associated restrictions/threats, for example, but with the help of FLIARA, they can, and will, quickly 'flourish'.

As for the green and blue frame, on one hand they represent the land and sky, which is also apt in relation to the rural and farming, but on a deeper level the green represents that women are 'grounded', and measured in their decisions about innovative practices, whilst at the same time, the sky is the limit in relation to what they can and want to achieve – and this is represented by blue.

Figure 1. Main Logo

CE, under WP6, has adapted the logo for communication and dissemination purposes. The adaptation process includes the redesign of all elements from the original logo:

Figure 2. Redesigned elements

To ensure proper use on all types of platforms, in both offline and online, different versions of the logo have been designed to allow its application on different backgrounds ensuring it to be easily visible for end-users. It will always be advisable to use the main version of the logo, but where this proves difficult for technical reasons, the following versions may be used. The figure below is an alternative black and white version of the main logo:

Figure 3. Black and white Logo

Other variations of the logo have been devised to complement the elaboration of communication materials. The following versions could be use in terms of contrast and background:

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Figure 4. Logo variations

The grid design element has been developed in order to help maintain a cohesive and balanced composition, ensuring that the logo is visually pleasing and easy to comprehend. Additionally, the grid structure lends itself well to scalability and adaptability. The clear divisions and geometric shapes enable the logo to be easily resized without losing its legibility or visual impact.

Figure 5. Grid Logo

In addition, when elaborating and using the logo on materials, it is essential to respect the safe space around the logo. The safe space refers to the area surrounding the logo that should remain free from any other elements, such as text, images, or graphics. Respecting the safe space ensures that the logo is visually distinct, legible, and maintains its impact.

Figure 6. Safe space Logo

For the FLIARA's logo to be perfectly identifiable and legible, it is recommended that the measurements should be as follows when using, printing or attaching it to a document:

Figure 7. Logo minimum sizes

The main colours of the project were extracted from the original version developed by Galway team. The following figure visually represents these colours with the respective HEIX codes to be used when applying it on digital or printing materials:

Figure 8. Main colours

Moreover, to reinforce the visual identity and personality of the documents and promotional materials of the project, a series of graphic elements are available in a diverse range of colours and shapes that adapt to the different materials that can be used.

Figure 9. Graphic elements

Two types of typography will be used in accordance with this visual identity:

Figure 10. Typography

Main Typography: Arial	Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Ññ Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz
Secondary Typography: Playfair Display	Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Ññ Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

The FLIARA project visual identity has two different typographies. The typeface family “Arial” has been chosen given that is a likeable, modern, and has excellent legibility both in print and on digital screens. This legibility is particularly valuable when creating promotional materials or websites that require quick comprehension and engagement.

As a secondary typography, an elegant and versatile font has been selected. “Playfair Display” is a font that ensures readability across various mediums, making it ideal for conveying important information effectively. Furthermore, it renders beautifully on screens, ensuring optimal user experience for websites and other digital platforms.

2.3.2. PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS

To promote the main ideas of this project a graphic layout has been created with the defined colours and typefaces which will be used in all the dissemination kit material.

It is important to mention that all these materials are available on the shared Microsoft Teams common folder, and some of them are also available on the FLIARA’s website. They include:

- **Roll-up**

A standardised roll-up has been developed to be used by every partner to assist in any on-site event to advertise in their institutions to gain visibility. A QR code might be added to the layout before printing to drive traffic the FLIARA website. Its measures are 85 cm x 200 cm.

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Figure 21. Roll-Up

- **Leaflet**

A leaflet has been developed to provide a brief and comprehensive overview of the project's objectives in triptych format with the dimensions of an A4 size sheet. It is a valuable tool for disseminating the project's activities and outcomes, increasing awareness and engagement among stakeholders, and promoting synergies and networking with complementary initiatives. Its design may vary over the lifespan of the project. The following figure (12) represents the first version of the leaflet which will be progressively adapted over the lifespan of the project:

Figure 12. Leaflet

- **Flyer**

An A5 size flyer has been designed as it is considered as an important means to communicate information about the challenges, objectives and vision of the project and it is easy to share across digital channels. When needed a QR code will be added to the layout to drive traffic to the project's website. See figure (13) below:

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Figure 13. Flyer

- **Folder**

The following customised folder serves as a visual representation of the project's brand, logo, and messaging. It can be used by the partners during relevant events and meetings. Its dimensions are specifically to hold A4 size documents.

Figure 14. Folder Template

- **ID Card**

A template for tailored identification cards has been created to serve as a visual representation of the project, showcasing its logo, colours and design elements. They contribute to a polished and organised event experience, leaving a positive impression on attendees and stakeholders, while promoting the project's identity and objectives.

Figure 15. ID Card Template

- **Templates**

Some documents and presentation templates based on the logo and colour palette were produced at the beginning of the project to begin awareness of brand identity and to develop coherency and consistency. All these templates are available on the Teams shared folder of the FLIARA project. Both official documents and deliverables templates produced are presented below:

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Figure 16. Official document template

Figure 17. General document template

For project deliverables a general template has been created. This contains the projects' standard visual identity with options to customise with styles, shapes, charts, use of headings, tables and figures.

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Figure 18. Deliverable front-page Template

Figure 19. Deliverable Template

The image shows a form for a deliverable template. It is titled 'Funded by the European Union' at the top left. The form is divided into two main sections: 'VERSION HISTORY' and 'DELIVERABLE INFORMATION'. The 'VERSION HISTORY' section contains a table with columns for 'Ver.', 'Date', 'Comments/Changes', and 'Author/Reviewer'. The 'DELIVERABLE INFORMATION' section contains various fields for project details, including Project Acronym, Project Title, Type of action, Topic, Project Start Date, Project Duration, Work Package, Deliverable, Date Due, Submission Date, Dissemination Level, Deliverable Description, Version, Status, Author(s), and Dissemination. The form is designed with a purple header and footer.

Ver.	Date	Comments/Changes	Author/Reviewer
1.1	00000000	First draft version to ...	(Name of author/reviewer)
1.2	00000000	Final draft reviewed by ...	(Name of author/reviewer)

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

Project Acronym: FLARA
 Project Title: FLARA: Ferenk-LIFE Innovatív in Agriculture and Rural Areas
 Type of action: HORIZON-RIA
 Topic: HORIZON-CLE-022-COMM-INTACT-01-01
 Project Start Date: 01/01/2023
 Project Duration: 36 months
 Work Package: [01/01/2023-04/01/24]
 Deliverable: [Deliverable 1.00]
 Date Due: 00/00/00
 Submission Date: 00/00/00
 Dissemination Level: PU
 Deliverable Description: [short description for deliverable]
 Version: 01
 Status: Not start
 Author(s): [Name of author(s)] [Name]
 Dissemination: [Deliverable]

Throughout the project, conferences and meetings will be held. For this, several templates have been developed for use during these events such as the Agenda Template, Presentation Template and Zoom Background.

Figure 20. Agenda template

The PowerPoint templates represent one of the most important tools for the development of strong and consistent presentations. CE has created a Smart Slide template with different layouts aimed at the easy elaboration of presentations over the lifespan of the project according to FLIARA visual identity.

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Figure 21. PPT Templates

The following online background provides a visually appealing and consistent backdrop during virtual meetings. By incorporating the project's logo, colours and design elements into the background during online meetings, participants are immersed in the project's visual identity, fostering a sense of unity and belonging.

Figure 22. Online Meeting Background Design

2.3.3. SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNELS

The FLIARA project aims to use social media platforms such as Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, and Instagram as part of its D&C strategy. The project's approach is to use these platforms to promote FLIARA and share updates on the project's progress, results, and events, while also engaging with target groups and stakeholders. Partners are suggested to use their own institutional social media accounts to share posts about FLIARA (see Annex 3).

In addition, the project will use social media to create and foster a community around the project, encouraging stakeholders to participate and share their thoughts and ideas. CE will actively monitor and respond to comments and feedback on social media, using this information to improve the project's communication and engagement strategies.

- **Twitter**

A dedicated FLIARA Twitter account has been created to communicate instantly and engage with the project's target audiences, particularly policy makers.

Table 2. Content strategy for Twitter

	@FLIARA_Project https://www.twitter.com/fliara_project
	Short updates on project progress, such as completed milestones and upcoming events.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 📌 Engaging tweets using relevant hashtags to reach a wider audience, such as #WomenInAg, #WomenAgri, #RuralInnovation, and #SustainableFarming. 📌 News related to the project's goals and objectives. 📌 Quotes and insights from project partners and experts on women-led innovations in agriculture and rural areas. 📌 Infographics and statistics related to the project's impact. 📌 Live tweets from project meetings or events.
--	--

● **Facebook**

Another important channel for communication efforts and disseminating the FLIARA project is Facebook. Facebook, with its large user base and diverse audience, has a broad reach and makes it possible to publish project updates, news articles, success stories, and essential resources relating to women's empowerment in agriculture. The aim is to inspire meaningful interactions and boost collaboration and knowledge exchange among stakeholders by leveraging engaging blogs, videos, and interactive features related to the project.

Table 3. Content strategy for Facebook

	<p>FLIARA Project</p> <p>https://www.facebook.com/fliara.project</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 📌 Project updates and news articles related to women empowerment in agriculture. 📌 In-depth articles or blog posts about specific innovative initiatives supported by FLIARA. 📌 Live videos or recorded webinars featuring expert discussions on rural development topics. 📌 Sharing relevant articles or reports from partner organisations, stakeholders and other relevant institutions across the EU. 📌 Calls to action encouraging community engagement, such as sharing personal experiences or ideas. 📌 Promoting upcoming events, workshops, or training sessions organised by FLIARA.

- **Instagram**

Instagram has been established as an essential communication and dissemination medium for the FLIARA project. This social media channel gives a fantastic opportunity to highlight the project's activities, accomplishments, and the inspiring stories of female agricultural and rural innovators. Instagram also allows FLIARA to communicate with the target audience in a visually appealing and impactful way by leveraging visual content such as images and videos. The main objective is to increase awareness, encourage dialogue, and inspire positive change in the agriculture sector through carefully picked posts.

Table 4. Content strategy for Instagram

	<p>@fliara_project</p> <p>https://www.instagram.com/fliara_project</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 📷 Photos and videos showcasing project activities and progress. 📷 Inspirational quotes related to agriculture and rural areas. 📷 Infographics highlighting key statistics and achievements of the project. 📷 Interactive polls or quizzes related to agriculture and rural development on Instagram Stories. 📷 Photos or audio testimonials from project beneficiaries. 📷 Use relevant hashtags to reach a wider audience, such as #WomenInAg, #RuralInnovation, #SustainableFarming and other hashtags included in section 3.1.1.

- **LinkedIn**

This profile has been created with the objective of communicating the project's information, results, and events to a large community of professionals, policy makers, innovation agents and, more generally, to business/industry representatives related to the fields of agriculture and farming. LinkedIn will be used as follows:

Table 5. Content strategy for LinkedIn

	<p>FLIARA Project</p> <p>https://www.linkedin.com/company/fliara-project/</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 📷 Photos and videos from project events and activities.

- 📌 Project updates on progress.
- 📌 Share relevant news articles, research papers, or publications related to women in agriculture and rural areas.
- 📌 Encourage audience engagement by asking questions or running polls related to agriculture, innovation, or rural development.
- 📌 Share educational content, such as tips, resources, or best practices for women in agriculture and rural entrepreneurship.
- 📌 Promote upcoming webinars, workshops, or events related to the project and invite audience participation.

Using targeted posts on social media platforms, FLIARA can refine its messaging and engage with people and organisations who are passionate about promoting change in these areas. The WP6 team from CE will regularly monitor and respond to social media comments, using this data to improve the project's communication and engagement tactics. Each social media platform has its own audience, and specialised content will be generated over the lifespan of the project to increase traffic to the website and among FLIARA social media channels by increasing followers, to gain more content's shares and raise awareness. Simultaneously, a strong social media strategy is critical to the project's success in reaching its target audience and fulfilling its D&C objectives.

To track progress and build networks, a table has been built as a database and contains all of the social network addresses of the partners, making it possible to exchange information and material with other partners. Through connecting and grouping the partners, this will enable the project to have a stronger and more organised online presence. The social networks of the partners are included in the annexes section of the present deliverable.

2.3.4. WEBSITE

Building on the developed visual identity and the logo, a well-designed and user-friendly website is essential for a good communication of the project. In this sense, D6.4 has been submitted to the EC regarding the Project Website development in the fourth month of the project. The website's communication functionalities are outlined below both the frontend and the backend:

2.3.4.1 FRONTEND

The frontend is essential to the success of a website, as it is the first thing that users see when they visit the site. A good frontend should be visually appealing, easy to navigate, and responsive to different screen sizes and devices. It must also be optimised for fast loading times, as users are more likely to abandon a website if it takes too long to load. The FLIARA website responds to all of the elements in its design.

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Figure 23. Website 1

What is FLIARA about?

FLIARA will heighten visibility and awareness of current female-led innovations, and their centrality and importance to achieving EU environmental and inclusion policies. FLIARA will demonstrate the innovative capacity of women in farming and in rural areas, with a particular focus on all four dimensions of sustainability (environmental, economic, social and cultural).

Women Led Innovations

200 innovative practices that contribute to a sustainable and viable rural environment identified in 10 European countries: Ireland, Netherlands, Germany, Czech Republic, Slovenia, Sweden, Finland, Spain, Romania and Italy

Community of Practice

A hub of networking and training amongst key actors and relevant stakeholders to exchange ideas, experiences and innovative knowledge, encouraging future female innovations and entrepreneurship

The Impact

FLIARA will challenge existing gender norms and stereotypes, increasing gender consciousness through a recognition and appreciation of the actual impact and economic value that women have in rural economies and rural development. The project will create practical tools and policy proposals to ensure that women are embedded in, and supported by, a more effective innovation ecosystem.

Foresight and Trend Analysis

FLIARA is currently working on its envisioning process to predict the role of women in the innovations required for sustainable farms and rural futures across EU Member States. These visions will be constructed by using an interactive foresight process, which will involve key stakeholders, at a local level creating a connection between their local contexts and sustainable futures.

Figure 24. Website 2

Funded by
the European Union

Figure 25. News & Events section on the Website

The homepage of the FLIARA website features a clean and modern design, with a prominent header that includes the project logo and menu. The main content area of the homepage features a slider with high-quality images and short descriptions of the project created to communicate the overall objective of FLIARA, along with links to more information. Below the slider, there are sections that highlight key project descriptions and news and events, with links to more detailed information.

The frontend of the www.fliara.eu website has been developed using modern web technologies, specifically HTML, CSS and JavaScript. The website uses a responsive design approach, which means it adjusts its layout and content to fit different screen sizes, from large desktops to small mobile devices. This makes the website accessible to a wider public, regardless of the device they are using to access it.

In particular, the frontend of the www.fliara.eu website has been developed with a focus on user experience and accessibility, using modern web technologies and a responsive design approach. The website features a clean and modern design with intuitive navigation and clear calls to action, making it easy for users to find the information they need and engage with the project.

2.3.4.2 BACKEND

On the other hand, a backend is the part of the website that the user does not see, which includes the server, application, and database that manage and store the website's data. It is responsible for processing requests from the frontend, generating dynamic content, and managing user data as outlined in D6.4 FLIARA Project Website. The backend is what powers the functionality and interactivity of a website, such as user authentication, content management and database management. The table below outlines the definition of the main technologies used to develop the FLIARA website components:

Table 6. Definition of backend terms:

Term	Definition
PHP (Hypertext Preprocessor)	A server-side scripting language used to create dynamic websites and web applications.
WordPress	A free and open-source CMS used for website content and structure management.
MySQL (Structured Query Language)	An open-source relational database management system used to store and manage website data.

In the case of www.fliara.eu, the backend has been built using a combination of server-side scripting languages such as PHP and a content management system (CMS) such as WordPress. PHP is a popular open-source server-side scripting language used to create dynamic websites and web applications. It is often used in conjunction with a CMS like WordPress, which provides a user-friendly interface for managing website content and structure.

WordPress is a free and open-source CMS that allows users to create and manage websites without having to write any code. It is widely used for its flexibility, ease of use, and maintenance. WordPress also supports various plugins and themes that can be used to add additional functionality and customise the website's appearance.

The CE Information Technology (IT) department has developed the FLIARA website CMS in WordPress for the correct smooth and navigability of the platform in preparation of future changes and new features as the project progresses. Also, a series of tools have been created from scratch based on the Project Website in the backend, so that WP6 can correctly publish, edit, delete content and perfectly run the platform.

To store and manage data, the backend of www.fliara.eu integrates a database management system such as MySQL. MySQL is a popular open-source relational database management system that is often used with PHP and WordPress. It is designed to handle large volumes of data and provide fast access to that data. MySQL can be used to store and manage a wide range of data types, including text, images, and multimedia.

The FLIARA project's website, exemplifies the importance of its integration, with a frontend that has been designed with user experience in mind, and a backend that is powered by PHP and WordPress and managed through a MySQL database. The end result is a website that can be easily navigated by users across the EU and beyond, with a high level of security and performance, and that is optimised for search engines, allowing for maximum visibility and reach.

2.4. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

2.4.1. PRESS RELEASES

Press releases are an important component of the FLIARA communication and dissemination strategy, which aims to connect with traditional dissemination channels, particularly those relevant to women working and living in rural areas, such as agricultural press and education and training platforms. Press releases not only contribute to highlighting a brighter future for women in rural areas across Europe, but also can lend support to their importance in achieving EU environmental and inclusion policies.

The publication of at least 20 press releases in different media has been sought, playing a crucial role in enhancing its visibility and impact. The press releases will also aid in forging linkages with agricultural press, policy makers and education and training platforms, while also reaching out to women living and working in rural areas. As outlined in the **section 5.3.6** of the present deliverable, project partners have already made significant progress in the development of press releases by showcasing FLIARA to a wider audience and creating greater awareness of the project and its goals.

2.4.2. NEWSLETTER

FLIARA aims to keep its stakeholders informed and updated about its progress, activities, and achievements throughout the project's duration. A newsletter will be issued biannually, starting from June 2023 and serve as an update on the project's accomplishments, initiatives, and relevant information. The newsletter will be distributed to both consortium members and external subscribers, with English as the default language. The feasibility of translating the newsletter into other project partner languages will be evaluated by the Consortium, and each partner will assume responsibility for its translation.

The design of the newsletter will align with the project's visual identity and will be made available in both HTML and PDF formats. To compile each newsletter edition, active

participation from partners is essential. Partners contributions are requested two weeks prior to the scheduled release of each newsletter. The table below outlines the timeline, main content sections, and the deadline for partner contributions (subject to project needs and outcomes):

Table 7. Partner’s contribution

Issue No.	Contributions by Partners	Release Date	Content
1	May 30, 2023	June, 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Introduce the Project ● Presenting 4 Partners (Their role) ● Introducing the Stakeholder Advisory Board ● FLIARA Conceptual Framework ● Women-led Innovation Research Review ● Future Vision Manifestations ● Campaign of Visibility ● Kick-off Meeting ● Attended Events ● Sister Projects (if applicable)
2	November 30, 2023	December, 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Presenting 6 Partners (Their role) ● Progress, news, and updates on ongoing activities ● Sustainability Innovations ● Female-led innovations: Europe ● Future events
3	May 28, 2024	June, 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Presenting 5 Partners (Their role) ● Feature on innovative case studies ● Project news and results ● Attended Events

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Future events • Policy Benchmarking: Summary of the assessment • Community of Practice network
4	November 29, 2024	December, 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Announcement of new collaborations for the • Project's final year: What's coming next? • Results of the case studies by country (Fact sheets) • Community of practice network events for 2025 • Practice Abstracts – (Batch 1) Dissemination
5	May 31, 2025	June, 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project News • Summary of outputs • Final Conference Invitation • FLIARA Toolkit Announcement • Collaborations • Attended events
6	November 28, 2025	December, 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final project summary and future outlook • Final Project News, including a final conference • A summary of the major findings and conclusions from the FLIARA experience • Practice Abstracts – (Batch 2) Dissemination • Following actions to exploit and sustain project outcomes throughout time

The newsletter will also include updates on upcoming events, workshops, and conferences related to the project, as well as new publications and other relevant information. It is important to note that the content for the newsletter will be drawn from the communication and dissemination material prepared throughout the project, ensuring that it is aligned with the overall project goals and strategies.

To register for the FLIARA project newsletter, stakeholders are invited to use the subscription box available on the project's website, specifically in the news section. The newsletter distribution follows the European Union General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) guidelines and is facilitated through a dedicated Newsletter Plug-In for Wordpress, ensuring compliance and data protection. Detailed information on GDPR compliance can be found at the following link: [GDPR Compliance Details](#). Therefore, all newsletters will be published in a dedicated section hosted on the FLIARA website, which can be accessed at <https://fliara.eu/newsletters/>.

Subscription to the newsletter is voluntary, and recipients will have the option to unsubscribe at any time using the provided opt-out link in each issue. For the FLIARA project, it is essential to have a legal basis, namely consent, to process personal data in the newsletter database. Therefore, the project relies on voluntary, specific, informed, and unambiguous consent from subscribers. A written record will be maintained to verify that proper consent has been obtained, clearly indicating when and how individuals have agreed to the processing of their personal data. Consent will be explicit and require clear affirmative action, ensuring transparency by using straightforward language and removing pre-ticked consent boxes.

Individuals who subscribe to the FLIARA newsletter and register for meetings or events enter their email address, which is required for newsletter delivery, as well as additional optional information. FLIARA will notify subscribers ahead of time about the purpose and use of their data. In compliance with GDPR regulations, CE, as the partner responsible for FLIARA's communication and dissemination activities, will process subscribers' data lawfully and fairly. Appropriate technical and organisational security measures will be implemented to safeguard the data, solely for the purpose of newsletter distribution and to generate anonymous and aggregated statistics upon request from the European Commission. Personal data collected will be stored safely by CE and will not be shared with other consortium members or external stakeholders.

To promote newsletter subscriptions, the invitation will be advertised on the project website and various social media channels. All consortium partners will be encouraged to invite selected international and local stakeholders to subscribe. Additional methods for promotion may include featuring the opt-in link on Facebook and Instagram, promoting the newsletter during FLIARA events, incorporating social media campaigns and subscription options in registration forms, and designing banners for publication on various websites, including partner sites and other digital channels such as the QR codes.

2.4.3. MULTIMEDIA AND NEWS TOOL

The FLIARA project's website hosts a powerful Multimedia and News Tool, specifically designed to foster collaboration among consortium partners. This innovative functionality empowers partners to contribute and publish captivating content in the form of videos or podcasts that aim to inspire and promote women-led innovations in agriculture and rural areas across the European Union. Partners are provided with an 'Informed Consent

Template for Audio-visual Material' to ensure that all participants and stakeholders are aware of and agree to the use of their images and information in project-related materials.

Through leveraging their unique perspectives and expertise, partners can post engaging multimedia content that resonates with diverse audiences and ignites creativity and innovation.

The Multimedia Tool supports content publication in partners' respective languages, ensuring inclusivity and accessibility for stakeholders throughout the project's lifespan. To ensure quality and security, WP6 oversees the content approval process, ensuring that all published material aligns with the project's objectives and maintains the highest standards of excellence. The Multimedia Section on the FLIARA website serves as a vibrant hub of inspiration, fostering knowledge exchange, and driving the visibility and impact of women in agriculture and rural innovation. Members of the consortium with access can promote content through this platform by accessing: <https://www.fliara.eu/submit-post/>

Figure 26. Multimedia Tool

Multimedia tool

The screenshot shows a web form for submitting multimedia content. It includes a 'Title' field with a placeholder 'Here goes a Title'. Below that is a 'Featured Image' section with a 'Choose Files' button and the text 'No file chosen'. The 'Categories' section has a dropdown menu currently set to 'Videos'. The 'Meta fields' section contains four input fields: 'Name of the Author or Channel', a text field with '30', 'www.linktothecontent.com', and a 'Select language' dropdown menu. At the bottom left of the form is a purple 'PUBLISH' button.

A News Tool has been developed as part of the FLIARA project's commitment to knowledge dissemination and collaboration. The News Tool will actively involve consortium partners in sharing valuable insights and information. Through this intuitive platform, partners can contribute articles, summaries, and various written content to be disseminated across the project's website.

Partners can use the News Tool to highlight their accomplishments, research findings, relevant information, and ongoing project's progress in agriculture and rural areas. This collaborative strategy guarantees the project has a dynamic and informative online

presence, increasing exposure and encouraging the exchange of ideas and experiences among partners, stakeholders, and the larger community. The News Section on the FLIARA website serves as a vibrant source of up-to-date information and a testament to the collective efforts and expertise of the consortium partners. The tool can be accessed, by using the consortium's login details shared by CE at: <https://www.fliara.eu/submit-news/>

Figure 27. FLIARA news tool

FLIARA news tool

Title

FEATURED IMAGE (SUPPORTED EXTENSIONS: JPG, PNG) (MAX. RESOLUTION: 2500PX*2500PX)

Content

PARAGRA... **B** *I*

P = STRONG

Tags (write tag name and hit Enter) (main tags: Farming, Leadership and Rural)

2.4.4. EVENTS AND CONFERENCES

International conferences, congresses, seminars, exhibits, and fairs are effective ways of reaching out to various stakeholders, making them key components of the FLIARA Project's dissemination activities. The participation of project partners in such events will enhance the project's visibility and engagement with stakeholders and other European projects. Consortium partners are encouraged to participate in events they consider relevant for disseminating the project. In addition, WP6 will regularly publish potential physical or virtual events aligned with the dissemination strategy and promote relevant news on social media and the project website. WP6 Leader, with the support of project partners, will periodically map out events. Partners are requested to inform WP6 Leader about dedicated events their organisations are planning to organise or attend at the EU/national level.

2.4.5. VIDEOS AND PODCASTS

During the FLIARA project, a series of videos will be created to enhance stakeholder engagement and raise awareness of the project's objectives. These videos will serve as a visually appealing means to showcase project progress, highlight female-led

innovations, and create short video blogs. It is devised to open a Youtube Channel to upload all videos when produced. YouTube then will serve as a platform to disseminate and to extract the videos for easy sharing through partner websites and the FLIARA toolkit, ultimately increasing the project's visibility.

The videos will take various forms, including short video blogs, videos featuring female innovators, and case study videos detailing specific innovative projects. For instance, there will be 10 video blogs produced from a selection of 10 out of the **200 case studies** with a focus on their innovations. Additionally, **another 10 videos** will be produced to showcase female innovators from the Innovative Ambassadors to be selected under WP3. Relevant partners that will engage directly with 200 female innovators and entrepreneurs will cooperate with WP6 Leader CE to provide the necessary material such as clips and audios to support the production of the video blogs. This multimedia content will help to effectively communicate and disseminate to a wider audience, amplifying the impact and reach of the FLIARA Project.

Beyond video blogs, it is planned to create ten engaging podcasts (5 focused on farms and 5 on rural regions). The material shall mainly be produced in English as the consortium working language. Additional recordings in national languages might be considered and discussed when relevant as the project progresses. Partners involved directly with innovators are expected to support CE in the identification and engagement of podcasts' speakers, as well as the recording of certain audio materials as needed.

The project will therefore create compelling podcasts that not only highlight the achievements of women in farming and rural areas, but also motivate others to follow in their footsteps by using their experience in communications and their connections with the innovators. The podcasts will reflect the diversity of female-led innovations, encompassing a range of themes, geographies, and scales.

2.5. MONITORING AND EVALUATION

This section includes a thorough set of indicators and monitoring activities and calendar for tracking the performance of dissemination campaigns based on the requirements of the Grant Agreement. Monitoring and Evaluation activities outlines the specific monitoring and evaluation activities to be carried out, their schedule, and the respective responsibilities of the partners involved.

Table 10. Monitoring and Evaluation activities

Communication activity / tool	Indicators / data	Schedule / frequency of monitoring	Responsible partner
Website and social media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of visits • Number of posts • Number of cross-linking 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biannual 	CE
Participation to other events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Press release • Title of the event • Place and date • Number of attendants • Description of the participation • Pictures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All information to be filled/sent one week prior; • Pictures to be sent the day or the day after for communication purposes. 	Project partners
FLIARA's events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Press release, title of the event, place and date, number of attendants (signature list), description of the participation • Pictures • Number of posts related to the event 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information to be filled/sent two weeks prior; • Pictures to be sent the day or the day after for communication purposes; • Number of posts. 	Partner responsible for the organisation of the event
Dissemination report on communication and dissemination activities performed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name of the partner • Name of press release published, • N° of news published on the partner's website • N° of scientific articles • N° of local/national events attended • N° of international events attended • N° of appearances in local media (radio, tv, newspaper) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biannual 	Project partners

As part of the regular monitoring process coordinated by CE, partners will be periodically asked to provide information on the dissemination and communication activities they have undertaken. This includes organising events, publishing news and press releases, and delivering presentations at conferences. Drawing from the information provided by partners, CE can develop improvements for future WP6 activities and perform adjustments to the FLIARA dissemination, communication, and exploitation plan (See Annex 2).

In order to assess the impact of the project's outreach efforts, monitoring and evaluation indicators are needed. The indicators listed below can be used to measure progress and identify areas for development, but they also allow the project team to demonstrate the project's and its activities' impact to target groups.

Table 11. Monitoring and evaluation indicators

Communication activity / results	Indicator	Target
Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in national/EU events • International conference • N° of attendants to the international conference 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation to 6 events • 1 international conference in Brussels • 80 attendants
Newsletter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production of newsletter • Subscribers • Readers reached per issue 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 newsletters • 500 subscribers • 150 readers per issue
Press releases	N° of press releases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least published in total
Project website	Site visits per month	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10.000 site visits
Publications	N° of peer reviewed publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 3
Non-scientific publications	N° of publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 15
Factsheets	N° of factsheets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 200
Submission of abstracts	N° of abstracts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 14
Social media	Followers (LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, Instagram)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2000 followers in total
Videos	N° of videos produced	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 20 (video blogs and videos of women-led innovations)
Podcasts	N° of podcast produced	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 10
Webinars	N° of webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 1 for civil society organisations • At least 1 for researchers • At least 2 for policy makers
Community of Practice Networking Events	N° of events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 4
Gender Specific Guide to Innovation	N° of guides	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 1
Communication campaigns	N° of communication campaigns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least the 5 defined communication campaigns
Dissemination material	N° of prints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 1 roll up, 1 leaflet, 1 poster, 1 template for word and 1 for ppt
Project website	N° of visits throughout the project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developed and maintained throughout the project
Attendance at events	N° of attendance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 5 events will be attended throughout the project
Synergies with other projects	N° of Synergies with other projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 5

3. VISIBILITY CAMPAIGN

The FLIARA project aims to increase visibility and impact of women led innovations through a Visibility Campaign under Task 6.2. The first stage of the Campaign of Visibility has commenced in M06 through the promotion on the FLIARA website and sharing content and related content on social media networks.

This campaign will be updated in M18 under **D6.2 Plan for Dissemination and exploitation including Communication Activities - V2**. A variety of content will be created for this campaign, including generating educational, useful designs that support FLIARA's visibility and reach through quality content. The first version of the campaign will revolve around the principles of Inbound Marketing, creating content to attract potential users actively looking for related themes to FLIARA via the internet to reach a wider audience and spread the word about the FLIARA project.

Given that inbound marketing material can be shared on social media, it can gain popularity through word-of-mouth and influence users over the long run by connecting with them on various social media platforms and directing these users to the FLIARA website. Thus, dedicated content will be prepared under the connected social media strategy for the project and the FLIARA website, shaping the future and popularity of the upcoming FLIARA Toolkit. Below is a list of the themes that have been derived from FLIARA deliverables outlined below that will shape the first stage of the campaign from M01 to M18 and the type of social media content may vary according to the project's needs:

Table 12. Type of social media content for the first stage of the Campaign.

Origin of the Topic	Type of social media content	Content Description
D.1.1 FLIARA Conceptual framework	Infographic	A visual representation of the FLIARA conceptual framework explaining the different components.
	Blog Post	An in-depth article discussing the FLIARA conceptual framework, its development, and its importance in promoting women-led innovation in farming and rural areas.
D 1.2 Women-led Innovation	Video Interview	Interviews with researchers who have conducted the studies on women-led

Research Review		innovation in farming and rural areas, discussing their findings and their implications for policy and practice.
	Social Media Graphics	Share interesting statistics or quotes from research studies on women-led innovation in farming and rural areas in the form of graphics that can be shared on social media.
D 2.2 Future Vision Manifestations	Short Video Clips	Short videos featuring women farmers and rural entrepreneurs discussing their visions for the future of farming and rural areas, and how their innovations are contributing to that future.
	Interactive Map	Create an interactive map showcasing different innovative practices and solutions led by women in farming and rural areas, and how they contribute to a more sustainable and equitable future.
D 2.3 Sustainability Innovations	Photo Gallery	A collection of photos showcasing innovative and sustainable farming practices led by women, such as regenerative agriculture, agroforestry, and urban farming.
	Blog posts	In-depth articles or blog posts featuring case studies of women-led innovations that promote sustainability in farming and rural areas, highlighting the benefits and impact of these practices.
D 3.2 Inventory of female-led innovations	Testimonials	Quotes and stories from women who have successfully implemented innovative practices in farming and rural areas

	Podcast or Webinar	Host a podcast or webinar discussing the different innovative practices led by women in farming and rural areas, featuring interviews with female entrepreneurs and farmers who have developed these practices and involving the Project Coordinators.
	Blog Posts	Articles or essays discussing the importance of female-led innovations in farming and rural areas and providing insights on how to encourage and support these innovations.
	Social Media Interactions	Encourage partners and women-led innovators to make a dedicated post about FLIARA to cause recognition of the project in their virtual communities.

FLIARA partners involved on the aforementioned topics will be asked to prepare a summary of their activities, to make sure multimedia content is available for the visibility campaign over the lifespan of the project. This process will also help the WP6 leaders to boost the outreach of the outputs and findings of the project, when applicable. Moreover, partners are encouraged to consider the following contributions for WP6 to create informative and engaging material:

Table 13. Contributions from partners

Type of content	Contributions from partners
Infographics	Relevant data, statistics, and other information related to the project's outcomes.
Videos or photos	Footage or images of the project's outputs, events, or other activities.

Testimonials	Positive feedback from project participants, stakeholders or relevant quotes from innovators.
Participation of sister projects	Case studies, shared experiences, and best practices related to FLIARA projects.

The next phase of the Visibility campaign will consist of spotlighting 200 existing women-led innovations in ten different EU countries. Podcasts, Video Blogs and 200 fact sheets will be prepared, and the content will be uploaded to the website. Partners involved are requested to take into account the elaboration of these materials for the correct dissemination of the project and transmit a clear picture of the value of women-led innovations and how they play a key role on gender equality in agriculture and rural areas.

As the project progresses the campaign will be progressively updated according to the results. For this reason, WP6 will be in constant preparation of up-to-date content as it arises. Also, WP6 encourages partners to share information that can be used to develop various forms of content such as infographics, videos or photos, testimonials, and short-form videos. Infographics are an excellent way to present important information in a way that it is easy to understand and visually appealing. Videos or photos can be used to showcase the project's outputs and outcomes, giving viewers an idea of what the project has accomplished. Testimonials and the participation of other sister projects can also be used to demonstrate the positive impact of FLIARA projects. Finally, short-form videos can be shared on various platforms to provide brief capsules of information from FLIARA partners.

3.1. SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGN

Social media content is an essential component of the FLIARA's campaign of visibility. Through the strategic use of social media, the project can establish itself as a relevant hub in the field of women-led innovation in agriculture and rural areas and foster a community of stakeholders interested in promoting and supporting these initiatives.

To achieve this goal, WP6 team has developed a comprehensive set of social media guidelines. These guidelines were shared with all consortium members and presented during the project meeting held on March 30th, 2023. The guidelines provide clear and concise instructions on how to use social media platforms such as Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, and Instagram to disseminate and communicate project-related content effectively.

The guidelines include practices for creating and sharing content in their institutional channels, such as using relevant hashtags and tagging appropriate accounts, as well as guidelines on how to proceed when attending events and ideas of content to share with

the WP6 leader. These guidelines will help partners to deliver good quality content for social media aligned with the campaign of visibility all along the project’s duration and beyond.

The social media guidelines are included in Annex 1 of the present deliverable.

3.1.1. HASHTAGS

Hashtags are a way to disseminate and communicate information on most social media platforms. To expand the reach and take advantage of current trends, FLIARA will utilise different hashtags to categorise similar content and connect their project with others. By doing so, it will be easier to organise and group related content, and hashtags can encourage engagement among individuals. Table 15 below lists the newly created hashtags that can be used in addition to those that connect with FLIARA’s own media content.

Table 15. Hashtags.

Trending and media hashtags	
#Innovation	#WomenInAg
#WomenLedInnovation	#WomenInspiringWomen
#FLIARA	#GenderInEquality
#FLIARAEU	#RuralInnovation
#CommunityOfPractice	#RuralWomen
#Women	#RuralCommunity
#GenderEquality	#Sustainability
#FemaleLed	#HorizonEU
#RuralWomen	#Enviroment
#WomenAgri	

3.2. TRADITIONAL MEDIA STRATEGY

The members of the project represent a key component of this strategy; hence, they are encouraged to leverage their local media connections to promote the project during the lifetime of FLIARA and in line with the campaign. This could include interviews with local radio and TV stations, podcasts, and features in local magazines.

Through establishing relations with local media, the project can increase awareness and exposure of its innovative practices among the general public. This increased visibility will share knowledge and learnings of existing practices. In this sense, consortium

partners aligned with the project's communication team who will coordinate media outreach efforts and ensure a consistent message across all traditional channels. The following preliminary ideas are suggested:

Radio:

- ✉ Contact local radio stations, especially in rural areas and pitch a story about the FLIARA project and the women-led innovations happening in the region.
- ✉ Offer to participate in an interview or panel discussion to share more information about the project and its impact.
- ✉ Provide key talking points and quotes for the radio host to use during the segment.

Television:

- ✉ Pitch a story to local TV news stations about the FLIARA project and the women-led innovations taking place in the area.
- ✉ Offer to schedule an interview or provide b-roll footage of the project and its participants.
- ✉ Provide a press release or fact sheet about the project and its key messages.

Podcasts:

- ✉ Identify relevant podcasts in the agriculture or rural development space and pitch a story about the FLIARA project and its impact on women-led innovation in your locality.
- ✉ Offer to participate in an interview or provide a guest post for the podcast's website.
- ✉ Provide key talking points and quotes for the podcast host to use during the episode.

Magazines:

- ✉ Research relevant local or rural-agriculture magazines and pitch a story about the FLIARA project and the women-led innovations taking place in the region.
- ✉ Offer to provide a written piece or interview for the magazine, including photos or other multimedia assets.
- ✉ Provide a press release or fact sheet about the project and its key messages.

WP6 leader CE will provide support to relevant partners for material adaptation, graphics, and elaboration.

3.3. FLIARA NETWORKING EVENTS

3.3.1. COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE NETWORKING

Task 4.2 of **WP4** is responsible for organising four FLIARA Community of Practice Networking Events in **Ireland (M18)**, **Slovenia (M22)**, **Italy (M26)**, and **Sweden (M30)**. These event locations have been determined based on a geographically spaced typology established in WP3 and WP4, considering four macro-regional hubs. The networking events will bring together relevant stakeholders, including 20 women Innovation Ambassadors. These 20 women will be selected from case studies conducted during WP3. The Innovation Ambassadors, who are women leading innovative practices in farming and rural areas, will play a central role in these events.

The FLIARA Community of Practice Networking Events will serve as platforms for knowledge exchange, showcasing innovative practices, and fostering visibility for women in agriculture and rural innovation. The events will also facilitate engagement with key actors involved in rural and farming innovation, such as SCAR AKIS, EU and National AKIS Coordinating Bodies, EU and National CAP Networks, Policy Makers and the Stakeholder Advisory Board. These events aim to promote collaboration, share best practices, and provide valuable insights for policy development and implementation.

4. EXPLOITATION PLAN AND OPPORTUNITIES

4.1. EXPLOITABLE RESULTS AND ROADMAP

The FLIARA project will produce several exploitable results. The following table outlines each one of them:

Table 16. Results to be exploited.

WPs	Result to be exploited	Comment
WP1	Conceptual framework; Case Study Assessment and Selection Framework; Assessment of policy and legal frameworks to support policy benchmarking.	Dedicated activities, encompassing tasks 1.1 to 1.5, will be carried out as part of the Contextual Concepts and Assessment Frameworks in WP1. These activities will seek to enhance the current conceptual and practical understanding of women-led innovations in agriculture and rural areas. To achieve this, a roadmap has been developed, outlining the actions necessary to foster synergies and networking.
WP2	Envisioning Process, Innovation Process and the Assessment Process.	An Envisioning Process has been undertaken in WP2, fostering collaboration and synergies with a wide range of stakeholders who possess the capacity to plan and shape the future. These stakeholders include local farmers, entrepreneurs, policy makers, active citizens, representatives of NGOs, development, and advisory organisations, as well as research and educational institutions who possess intimate knowledge of agriculture and rural areas in the different national contexts of the project. The aim is to capture insights, perspectives, and expertise from various sectors and regions to form a solid foundation for the project's exploitation of results, as it ensures that the developed innovations and strategies are relevant, practical, and scalable across different national contexts within the European Union.
WP3	The Research Guidelines and Thematic Selection Methodology and the Comparative Analysis of the Case Studies by Country and Sustainability Innovation Dimension.	In WP3, the FLIARA project will undertake a comprehensive analysis of women-led and gendered innovations in farming and rural communities. Under tasks 3.1 and 3.4, the project will engage directly with 200 female innovators and entrepreneurs across ten different EU countries to uncover valuable insights, lessons, and success stories from these innovative women, which can then serve as a pathway to enhance the capacity of other rural and farm women to engage in similar innovative practices. The insights gathered from this analysis will inform future policies, initiatives, and capacity-building efforts.
WP4	Community of Practice Network and Toolkit.	In WP4, the FLIARA project will implement a multi-actor approach through the establishment of the FLIARA Community of Practice Network. In particular, Task 4.2 will focus on the execution of the four networking events, which will bring together relevant stakeholders, including the selected 20 innovation ambassadors, serving as platforms to engage with

		key actors currently involved in rural and farming innovation. Task 4.3 is closely linked to this, as it involves all partners in benchmarking EU and National policy and Legal Framework during the events. This will be achieved through focus groups and workshops where the findings will be discussed, and key issues will be identified to be brought forward to policy design and assessment workshops. Furthermore, Tasks T4.4 and T4.5 will result in the creation of the FLIARA Toolkit, a user-friendly digital repository for transferring project generated knowledge to inspire both current innovative practitioners and future generations of innovative rural women.
WP5	Policy Booklet (Policy Recommendations).	In WP5, the FLIARA project aims to design more effective policy, legal, and governance knowledge and innovation systems, that will support and promote women-led innovation in farming and rural areas. Task 5.2 plays a crucial role in this process by engaging users and experts to explore the lessons learned and outcomes achieved throughout the FLIARA project. Task 5.3 is also relevant for exploitation purposes as it focuses on the development of new policy proposals based on the project's results. A supportive and inclusive policy framework will be created for replication to facilitate women-led innovation in farming and rural areas.

All the outcomes mentioned above will be made available to stakeholders at no cost, ensuring wide accessibility. The distribution of these results will be coordinated by the project partners and overseen by WP6, responsible for Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation. Various digital channels will be utilised, including the project website and open-access platforms, social media platforms, direct emails to regional stakeholders, targeted promotion to female innovators in agriculture and rural areas across the European Union, scientific papers, abstracts, organised events, and newsletters.

The FLIARA consortium will regularly evaluate the project's outcomes to determine if additional results should be exploited, ensuring their inclusion in future updates of this deliverable. More concrete actions for long-term sustainability of FLIARA results will be agreed among the consortium towards the end of the project.

4.2. TARGET USERS FOR EXPLOITATION

The successful exploitation of FLIARA's research work hinges on the identification and engagement of target users. To ensure effective communication and interest in project developments, the consortium has devised a comprehensive plan that establishes clear target audiences for dissemination defined in Section 2.2 of this deliverable.

Throughout the project's duration, dissemination activities will lay the foundation for exploitation by fostering a robust network of stakeholders and maintaining their involvement in FLIARA's initiatives. Consequently, the identified target audiences will

also serve as prime targets for exploitation efforts, as they are the most likely to exhibit interest in and derive value from the project's results.

FLIARA aims to maximise the impact and reach of its outcomes through:

- 🏛️ **Governments and policy makers:** Collaboration with governmental bodies and decision makers / policy makers will facilitate the integration of FLIARA's findings into policy frameworks, driving positive change in agricultural and rural sectors while also considering gender-based perspectives. An active involvement of policy makers in several actions of the project will facilitate the alignment of FLIARA's recommendations with existing policies, strengthening their implementation and impact.
- 🏛️ **Innovation Support Services:** Close cooperation with innovation support services will enable the translation of research into practical applications and promote the adoption of innovative practices.
- 🏛️ **Academia and scientific communities:** Engagement of academic institutions will foster knowledge exchange, scholarly contributions, and the incorporation of FLIARA's research outcomes into educational curricula. Collaboration with the scientific community will foster peer-reviewed publications, research collaborations, and the validation of FLIARA's findings.
- 🏛️ **Civil Society:** Engaging civil society organisations will help disseminate the project's results to wider audiences, raising awareness and promoting inclusive dialogue on gender equality in agriculture and rural areas.
- 🏛️ **Farming Community and Rural Society at Large:** The farming community and rural society are at the heart of FLIARA's mission. By directly engaging with farmers, rural entrepreneurs, and local communities, the project aims to empower and support their innovative initiatives, ensuring the practical applicability of its outcomes.

Through targeted dissemination and exploitation strategies, FLIARA seeks to harness the collective potential of these key user groups, driving sustainable and inclusive development in agriculture and rural areas across the European Union.

4.3. SYNERGIES AND NETWORKING WITH SIMILAR PROJECTS AND INITIATIVES

The FLIARA project recognises the importance of establishing connections with other initiatives and proposals that are directly related to or connected with this call topic. Initiatives such as 'Smart Solutions for Smart Rural Communities' (HORIZON-CL6-2022-COMMUNITIES-02-01-two-stage) and 'Deepening the Functioning of Innovation Support' (HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-24) serve as valuable resources for knowledge exchange and collaboration. Through engaging with these initiatives, as well as existing and future Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) networks like the EIP-AGRI Support Facility and the European Network for Rural Development, the FLIARA Project's Community of Practice Network (WP4), Policy Design and Assessment (WP5), and

Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (WP6) will contribute to the enhancement of national and international research and innovation activities.

Through these collaborative efforts, the FLIARA project will establish networks and facilitate knowledge flows among key actors involved in the call topic. This collaboration will have a broader impact on the implementation of the Horizon Europe strategic plan for 2021-2024, particularly in areas such as 'Climate change mitigation and adaptation', 'Sustainable food systems from farm to fork', and 'Inclusive growth and new job opportunities'.

It is necessary for the project to identify possible synergies and networking opportunities which will help to achieve dissemination, exploitation and communication purposes and build a solid reputation and raise awareness around the project's objectives, activities and expected outcomes. To achieve this, a mapping exercise using results from Task 1.2 has identified some initial projects with connections and similarities with FLIARA. See table 17 below. This list will be periodically updated based on new projects and new collaborations forged. At this stage of the project links with the following projects have been already established through communication activities such as, the FLIARA online forum held in M06, FLIARA Link Meetings and participation in conferences:

Table 17. Liaison with EU-funded projects

Project	Website
GRASS CEILING	http://www.grassceiling.eu/
SWIFT	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101084561
SafeHabitus	https://www.safehabitus.eu/
ATHENA	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101006416
DEMETER Project	https://h2020-demeter.eu/
EU-FARMBOOK	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060382
COEVOLVERS	https://co-evolvers.eu/
AURORAL	https://www.auroral.eu/#/
PREMIERE Project	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101086531
GENDERACTION+	https://genderaction.eu/
Tools4Cap	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101086311
DESIRA	https://desira2020.agr.unipi.it/

4.3.1. EU FARMBOOK

Among similar projects and initiatives, it is worth highlighting that to ensure a seamless integration of its efforts, the FLIARA project will establish close collaboration with the Horizon Europe multi-actor project, EU FarmBook, which encompasses all 27 Member States. EU FarmBook serves as a centralised repository of vetted best practices for farmers and foresters, with its content contributed by Horizon-funded projects. FLIARA recognizes the immense potential of this powerful platform and intends to leverage it for effective dissemination purposes.

FLIARA positions itself to broaden the scope of its research outputs and ensure their accessibility to a broader audience through strategic engagement with EU FarmBook, available at <https://eufarmbook.eu/>. The existing user base of the platform represents a

valuable community of stakeholders who can benefit from and contribute to FLIARA's activities. FLIARA not only improves its dissemination efforts by actively participating in EU FarmBook, but it also maximises the possibility for knowledge sharing, collaboration, and further use of its research products.

4.4. INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS STRATEGY

The FLIARA project recognises the importance of managing Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) in accordance with the guidelines outlined in the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement, adhering to Horizon Europe principles. The rules for the utilisation of foreground and background knowledge, as well as for the handling of sensitive and confidential information are defined in the FLIARA Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. FLIARA will assess the results over the lifespan of the project and their potential for exploitation, incorporating them into the project's exploitation plan outlined in the final version of the present deliverable (D6.3) in Month 36.

On the other hand, one of the key objectives of the FLIARA project is to create a freely accessible Toolkit on the project's website, aimed at promoting and supporting women-led innovation in agriculture and rural areas without any IPR restrictions. To ensure future sustainability, an IPR checklist will be implemented, requiring publishing partners to confirm that their publications do not contain exploitable content. Furthermore, there will be no IPR barriers to the continued use of project materials by end-users after the project's completion. It can be anticipated that the website and associated materials may be transferred to the European Commission or to a follow-on project supporting women-led innovation in farming and rural areas, such as the case of the EU FarmBook project, to facilitate their continued availability and support.

4.5. OPEN SCIENCE

FLIARA is committed to adhering to the principles and practices of Open Science and Open Access throughout the project's lifecycle, from its inception to completion. This includes depositing FLIARA public data in trusted open-access repositories, in compliance with HE rules on open access, and under open licences. Article 17 of the HORIZON Europe Model Grant Agreement and its Annex 5 outline the Open Science principles that FLIARA will follow. The project will share anonymised scientific data and knowledge in a transparent and non-discriminatory manner to relevant knowledge actors, including project partners and the wider stakeholder community, as early and openly as possible in the research process. This will be achieved through pre-registration, registered reports, and preprints.

By implementing Open Science practices as part of the project's methodology, FLIARA will provide key stakeholders with an opportunity to co-design and contribute to the research effort. This transparency throughout the research process not only facilitates valuable feedback and increased collaboration opportunities but also increases the validity and community confidence in the resulting outreach activities. The accumulation of knowledge resulting from the project's Open Science practices will not only increase the uptake of scientific research results and reproducibility of research outputs but will

also help avoid duplication of research efforts and funding streams, ultimately enhancing the overall impact of the project on society.

On the other hand, FLIARA is committed to making peer-reviewed publications openly accessible through trusted repositories, whether the publication is free of charge or not. To achieve this goal, immediate open access will be ensured through a trusted repository. The publications will subsequently be published in **Open Research Europe** and/or other open access peer-reviewed scientific journals, with the content licensed for reuse. This will not only enhance the accessibility and visibility of FLIARA's research outcomes but also increase the potential for broader knowledge sharing, collaboration, and impact. The following platforms are initially suggested to disseminate the FLIARA project and will be reviewed throughout the project duration:

- 🏠 **CORDIS**: Known as well as the Community Research and Development Information Service, is the European Commission's primary public repository for information on all EU-funded research projects and their outcomes. CORDIS provides a wide range of information about research funding opportunities, project results, policy developments, and news related to research and innovation in the European Union. Researchers can use CORDIS to find information about past and ongoing EU-funded projects, search for partners and collaborators, and access research results and publications. The European Commission's primary repository for information on EU-funded research projects and their outcomes. FLIARA's approved public deliverables will be made available on this platform once approved by the EC.
- 🏠 **The Horizon Results Platform**: This is a portal where participants of the Framework Programme can share their research outcomes with policy makers, investors, entrepreneurs, researchers, and interested citizens. FLIARA can also publish their results on this platform to reach a broader audience.
- 🏠 **EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD (EOSC)**: It is an initiative of the European Commission that aims to create a trusted and secure space where researchers and scientists can store, manage, curate, and share their data and results with others. The establishment of a globally accessible communication channel with the EOSC portal will enable FLIARA to store, curate, and share their scientific data and results under well-defined and trusted conditions. This will make FLIARA's research more accessible to knowledge sources and knowledge actors across disciplines and countries, enabling collaboration and the creation of new knowledge and insights. The accessibility and openness of the EOSC portal will enhance the visibility and impact of FLIARA's research, while also facilitating collaboration with other researchers and institutions.
- 🏠 **ZENODO**: Zenodo is an open-access digital repository that allows researchers, scientists, and scholars to share and preserve their research outputs, such as datasets, software, images, videos, and publications. Zenodo is operated by

CERN (the European Organization for Nuclear Research) and is funded by the European Commission, which ensures its sustainability and long-term preservation. Zenodo assigns a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to every deposit, making it easy to cite and share research outputs. CE suggests uploading outputs and approved deliverables to this platform.

ARAN: Access to Research at University of Galway, a digital collection of open access scholarly publications. ARAN's purpose is to collect, preserve and make freely available scholarly communication, including peer-reviewed articles, working papers, and conference papers created by researchers affiliated with the University of Galway. FLIARA recognises the potential of ARAN as a valuable platform for disseminating its project outputs.

Providing open access to project outputs through collaborative dissemination platforms will be an effective means of improving the accessibility and reusability of research outputs. In the case of the FLIARA project, this will increase the visibility and impact of its research by enabling a wider audience to access and use its results.

5. PROGRESS ON WP6 ACTIVITIES

5.1. WEBSITE

The FLIARA project website was established in April 2023, during Month 4 of the project, following the submission of D6.4, which outlined the website's structure. Since its initial setup, several changes have been implemented to enhance the user experience and functionality of the website:

- 🔗 **Visual Structure:** The website underwent modifications to improve accessibility and readability. These changes were aimed at ensuring that visitors can easily navigate and comprehend the content presented on the site.
- 🔗 **Events Section:** The events section of the website has been updated to enhance its indexability and provide a comprehensive listing of relevant project events. Additional events have been included to keep visitors informed about upcoming activities and opportunities to engage with the FLIARA project.
- 🔗 **Google Analytics Integration:** To track and analyse website visits throughout the project's duration, a Google Analytics tag with the Global site tag (UA-254936396-1, gtag.js) has been installed. This enables the project team to gain insights into website traffic and visitor behaviour, contributing to data-driven decision-making.
- 🔗 **Compliance and User Preferences:** To adhere to GDPR regulations and prioritise user privacy, a Cookies Policy has been incorporated into the footer section of the website. Additionally, a pop-up window has been implemented to inform visitors about the website's GDPR compliance and seek their consent regarding their preferences.

As an evolving platform, the FLIARA project website will be regularly updated to reflect new developments, emerging needs, and relevant information throughout the project's progression. It serves as a central hub for sharing and distributing project-related content on an ongoing basis. For more information, please visit the FLIARA project website at the following URL: <https://fliara.eu/>

5.2. SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORMS

FLIARA maintains an active online presence across various social media platforms, including Twitter, Instagram, Facebook, and LinkedIn. These accounts were established at the inception of the project and will be consistently updated throughout its duration to provide timely information on project outcomes, partners, organized events, interviews, noteworthy project-related events, as well as relevant updates and findings. As of June 2023, the following social media accounts have been created for FLIARA along with their corresponding posts and follower statistics:

- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/fliara.project>
 - Followers: 41
 - Posts: 27
- Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/fliara_project/

- Followers: 127
- Posts: 29
- Twitter: https://twitter.com/FLIARA_Project
- Followers: 344
- Tweets: 122
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/fliara-project/>
- Followers: 130
- Posts: 26

These social media accounts are key communication channels through which FLIARA ensures transparency, widespread dissemination of project outcomes, and engagement with stakeholders and the wider public. Through leveraging the power of social media, the project aims to create a vibrant online community, foster dialogue, and raise awareness about the importance of women's role in agriculture and rural areas across the European Union.

5.3. INSIGHTS

WP6 will monitor and track every communication and dissemination activity throughout the project, not only on the internet but as well on traditional press. At the submission of the present deliverable, FLIARA has reached the following performance on media and the Internet:

5.3.1. GOOGLE ANALYTICS

Figure 28. Google Analytics

Since April 1st, 2023, until today, the FLIARA website has recorded a total of 1,199 visitors. Out of these visitors, over the last 30 days, 209 are new users, indicating a growing interest in the project and its initiatives. The average engagement time on the website is 2 minutes and 11 seconds, demonstrating that visitors are spending a

significant amount of time exploring the content and resources available. These analytics reflect a positive trend in terms of user engagement and indicate that the FLIARA website is attracting and retaining the attention of its audience.

5.3.2. TWITTER IMPRESSIONS

Figure 29. Twitter impressions

From February 1st, 2023, until the present day, the FLIARA Project's Twitter account has achieved notable engagement and outreach. The account received 213 likes and 87 retweets, indicating positive reception and active participation from the audience. Impressions, which reflect the total number of times the content was displayed, reached a significant count of 8,838. This demonstrates the project's effective dissemination of its message to a wide audience, fostering increased visibility and potential impact.

5.3.3. FACEBOOK AND INSTAGRAM REACH

Figure 31. Instagram and Facebook reach indicators

Since February 1st, 2023, the FLIARA project has monitored the reach of its Facebook and Instagram accounts. The Facebook reach has reached a total of 2025, while the Instagram reach has reached 711. These insights provide valuable data on the project's visibility and audience engagement, helping to shape future strategies for maximising impact and awareness.

5.3.4. LINKEDIN IMPRESSIONS

Figure 32. LinkedIn Impressions

Since February 1st, 2023, until today, the FLIARA Project page on LinkedIn has made significant progress in terms of its online presence and engagement. FLIARA has received 248 reactions, indicating that our content resonates with our audience and elicits positive responses. Additionally, the project content on this platform has been reposted 58 times, indicating that the audience finds value in what FLIARA shares and wants to amplify the message. The outreach has reached 3,497 impressions, showcasing the wide reach and visibility of the project's mission and objectives.

5.3.5. MEDIA PRESENCE

Owing to the concerted dissemination of information from all the consortium about FLIARA on various social media channels, websites, and other online platforms, the project has received significant attention and interest from relevant stakeholders and audiences. This increased visibility has helped to promote the project's objectives, as well as to foster engagement and collaboration with other initiatives in the field. Through continuing to work together in this way, the project will be better positioned to achieve its goals and make a lasting impact on women-led innovations in agriculture and rural areas. Table 18 below lists all the press impact FLIARA has achieved:

Table 18. Media Presence

Featured	Title	Type of Content	Link
SuperScience	EU Horizon Europe Project: Female-Led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas "FLIARA"	Factsheet	https://www.superscienceme.it/corner-progetto/fliara-female-led-innovation-in-agriculture-and-rural-areas/
University of Ljubljana - Univerza v Ljubljani	Projekt FLIARA vzpostavlja podporno okolje za inovativnost žensk v kmetijstvu in na podeželju	FactSheet	http://www.drustvo-podezelje.si/images/drustvo/aktualno/2023/LAS_novice/%C5%A1tevilka_2/Fliara_izjava_za_javnost.pdf
Madam Business Prosperita	Role žen v zemědělství a venkovském životě	Magazine	https://www.iprosperita.cz/images/pdf_mb/madam_business_2023-03.pdf
Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development	FLIARA, GRASS CEILING and SWIFT: Supporting women-led innovation in rural areas	News	https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/agri/items/782608/en
Iberian Press	inicia FLIARA el proyecto europeo que apoyará las prácticas rurales innovadoras lideradas por mujeres	News	https://www.iberianpress.es/noticia/inicia-fliara-el-proyecto-europeo-que-apoyara-las-practicas-rurales-innovadoras-lideradas-por-mujeres/44569
Canarias 7	Mujeres de toda Europa liderarán la innovación rural a través del proyecto FLIARA	News	https://www.canarias7.es/economia/mujeres-europa-lideraran-20230127210835-nt.html

Desarrollo Local	Proyecto europeo FLIARA	News	https://desarrollolocal.emprenemjunts.es/?op=8&n=29228
Demeter	FLIARA: FEMALE LED INNOVATION IN AGRICULTURE AND RURAL AREAS	News	https://h2020-demeter.eu/fliara-female-led-innovation-in-agriculture-and-rural-areas/
Galway Pulse	University of Galway receives €3 million to enhance female innovation in agriculture and rural areas	News	https://galwaypulse.com/2023/02/18/agriculture-fliara/amp/
National Rural Network	European Project to Enhance Women's Role in Rural Life Launched	News	https://www.nationalruralnetwork.ie/farm-viability/farm-viability-news/european-project-to-enhance-womens-role-in-rural-life-launched/
CYSNEWS. CZ	Vědecký tým z MENDELU bude zkoumat roli žen ve venkovském životě	News	https://www.cysnews.cz/veda/vedicky-tym-z-mendelu-bude-zkoumat-rolu-zen-ve-venkovskem-zivote/
Red Rural Nacional	El proyecto europeo "FLIARA" saca a la luz las prácticas en innovación ejercidas por las mujeres rurales	News	https://www.redruralnacional.es/noticia/el-proyecto-europeo-fliara-saca-la-luz-las-practicas-en-innovacion-ejercidas-por-las
TU Delf	FLIARA - De rol van vrouwen in een duurzame toekomst voor het platteland	News	https://www.tudelft.nl/2023/bk/fliara-de-rol-van-vrouwen-in-een-duurzame-toekomst-voor-het-platteland
Hochschule für nachhaltige Entwicklung Eberswalde (HNEE)	Start für Verbundprojekt „FLIARA“ – Frauengeführte Innovationsprozesse in Landwirtschaft und ländlichem Raum	News	https://www.hnee.de/de/Aktuelles/Hochschulkommunikation/Pressemitteilungen/Start-fr-Verbundprojekt-FLIARA-Frauengefhrte-Innovationsprozesse-in-Landwirtschaft-und-lndlichem-Raum-E11716.htm
OpenAIRE Research Graph	FLIARA: Female-Led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas	News	https://beopen.openaire.eu/search/project?projectId=cordahe::312ece601a4933e1b85d0a9447adc49e
EUROPAPRESS	Una pyme canaria gestionará un proyecto de investigación sobre la innovación de mujeres en agricultura y zonas rurales	News	https://www.europapress.es/islas-canarias/noticia-pyme-canaria-gestionara-proyecto-investigacion-innovacion-mujeres-agricultura-zonas-rurales-20230131131649.html
TEAGSC	Horizon Europe project FLIARA to enhance women's role in rural life, agriculture and rural affairs	News	https://www.teagasc.ie/rural-economy/rural-economy/agricultural-economics/research/fliara/
Linnaeus University	FLIARA Kick-off meeting marks the	News	https://lnu.se/en/meet-linnaeus-university/current/news/2023/fli

	beginning of the project		ara-kick-off-meeting-marks-the-beginning-of-the-project/
Linnaeus University	Project: FLIARA – Female-Led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas	News	https://lnu.se/en/research/research-projects/project-fliara-female-led-innovation-in-agriculture-and-rural-areas/
Galway Daily	University of Galway launches project to enhance women’s role in rural life	News	https://www.galwaydaily.com/news/university-of-galway-launches-project-to-enhance-womens-role-in-rural-life/
Društvo za razvoj slovenskega podeželja	Projekt FLIARA vzpostavlja podporno okolje za inovativnost žensk v kmetijstvu in na podeželju	News	http://www.drustvo-podezelje.si/index.php?option=com_k2&view=item&id=1428:projekt-fliara-vzpostavlja-podporno-okolje-za-inovativnost-zensk-v-kmetijstvu-in-na-podezelju&Itemid=888&acm=89
Društvo za razvoj slovenskega podeželja	Projekt FLIARA - kakšno podeželje želimo?	News	http://www.drustvo-podezelje.si/novice/item/1469-ohranimo-travniske-sadovnjake
Društvo za razvoj slovenskega podeželja	Projekt FLIARA vzpostavlja podporno okolje za inovativnost žensk v kmetijstvu in na podeželju	News	http://www.drustvo-podezelje.si/novice/item/1428-projekt-fliara-vzpostavlja-podporno-okolje-za-inovativnost-zensk-v-kmetijstvu-in-na-podezelju
IndustriAmbiente	Comienza el proyecto europeo FLIARA que apoyará las prácticas rurales innovadoras lideradas por mujeres	News	https://www.industriambiente.com/noticias/20230127/comienza-el-proyecto-europeo-fliara-que-apoyara-las-practicas-rurales-innovadoras-lideradas-por-mujeres#.Y9PQesmZNPY
LaVanguardia	Una pyme canaria gestionará un proyecto de investigación sobre la innovación de mujeres en agricultura y zonas rurales	News	https://www.lavanguardia.com/local/canarias/20230131/8722164/pyme-canaria-gestionara-proyecto-investigacion-sobre-innovacion-mujeres-agricultura-zonas-rurales.html
That's Farming	University of Galway launches European-wide women in ag project	News	https://thatsfarming.com/farming-news/womens-role-in-rural-life/
AgriLand	University of Galway project to enhance women’s role in rural life	News	https://www.agriland.ie/farming-news/university-of-galway-project-to-enhance-womens-role-in-rural-life/
Irish America Magazine	University of Galway Launches EU Project to Enhance Women’s Role in Rural Life	News	https://www.irishamerica.com/2023/01/news-roundup-january-14/
Irish Farmers Journal	University of Galway launches project for women in agriculture	News	https://www.farmersjournal.ie/university-of-galway-launches-

			project-for-women-in-agriculture-744347
MENDELU	Vědecký tým z MENDELU bude zkoumat roli žen ve venkovském životě	News	https://mendelu.cz/vedecky-tym-z-mendelu-bude-zkoumat-rolu-zen-ve-venkovskem-zivote/?psn=200
Galway Advertiser	University of Galway launches European project to enhance women's role in rural life	News	https://www.advertiser.ie/galway/article/133459/university-of-galway-launches-european-project-to-enhance-womens-role-in-rural-life
Radio Faro del Noroeste	Mujeres de toda Europa liderarán la innovación rural a través del proyecto FLIARA	News	https://www.radiofarodelnoroeste.es/secciones/sociedad/item/13663-mujeres-de-toda-europa-lideraran-la-innovacion-rural-a-traves-del-proyecto-fliara
El Blog de Anna Conte	Mujeres de toda Europa liderarán la innovación rural a través del proyecto FLIARA	News	https://elblogdeannaconte.com/mujeres-toda-europa-lideraran-innovacion-rural-a-traves-proyecto-fliara/
MENDELU	Vědecký tým z MENDELU bude zkoumat roli žen ve venkovském životě	News	https://af.mendelu.cz/vedecky-tym-z-mendelu-bude-zkoumat-rolu-zen-ve-venkovskem-zivote/
Društvo za razvoj slovenskeg a podeželja	Projekt FLIARA - kakšno podeželje želimo?	News	http://www.drustvo-podezelje.si/novice/item/1469-ohranimo-travniske-sadovnjake
ProfiPress	Vědci z Mendelovy univerzity budou zkoumat roli žen v zemědělství	News	https://zemedelec.cz/vedci-z-mendelovy-univerzity-budou-zkoumat-rolu-zen-v-zemedelstvi/
Envi Web	Vědecký tým z MENDELU bude zkoumat roli žen ve venkovském životě	News	https://www.enviweb.cz/rss/305917
AGRÁRNÍ WWW PORTÁL	Vědecký tým z MENDELU bude zkoumat roli žen ve venkovském životě	News	http://www.agris.cz/clanek/221934
ZAHRADNIC TVI	Vědecký tým z MENDELU bude zkoumat roli žen ve venkovském životě	News	https://zahradaweb.cz/vedecky-tym-z-mendelu-bude-zkoumat-rolu-zen-ve-venkovskem-zivote/
ECOLISE & Communities for Future	Creating a regenerative and gender equal world	Newsletter	https://communitiesforfuture.org/civicrm/mailling/view/?id=137
Geografska širina	Projekt FLIARA - delavnica snovanja vizij za podeželje LAS Srce Slovenije	Newsletter	https://sites.google.com/view/geografskasirina/starej%C5%A1e-%C5%A1tevilke/2023/april-junij#h.emjlgal4gasu
DEMETER Project	Empowering Farmers - Demeter	Newsletter	https://mailchi.mp/a04532685a1d/demeter-newsletter-issue-8-march-16856757

EU Rural vision	Rural Pact Community Newsletter - March 2023	Newsletter	https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/agri/newsletter-archives/44644
Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development	EU Rural vision - Rural Pact Community Newsletter	Newsletter	https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/agri/newsletter-archives/44644
Red Rural Nacional	Boletín RRN - ENERO 2023	Newsletter	https://www.redruralnacional.es/boletines/enero-2023
EFEAGRO	Mundo Rural	Podcast	https://www.rtve.es/play/audios/mundo-rural/mundo-rural-desperdicio-alimentario/6811188/
PROMĚNY ZEMĚDĚLS TVÍ	Venkov se mění v konzum, role hospodáře se vytrácí. Projekt EU chce posílit úlohu žen	Podcast	https://zpravy.aktualne.cz/ekonomika/promeny-zemedelstvi/podcast-promeny-zemedelstvi-s-miladou-stastnou-z-mendelovy-u/r-6d55d326ca4811edba63ac1f6b220ee8/?fbclid=IwAR1-Hnp7R7eyDEHnv71iPp0HIIVPx80y7N3S-Vge3kVFzyUmp92FWx7TZLc
Agri-Insider	In Her Field, Episode 1: Professor Maura Farrell, University of Galway, 19.03.23	Video	https://agriinsider.tv/programs/in-her-field-episode-1-ad553e?offset=278

5.3.7. ATTENDED EVENTS

Significant efforts were made over the first six months of the FLIARA project to actively participate in numerous events, effectively promoting the project and building meaningful relationships with stakeholders (Table 19). These events provided a venue for FLIARA's objectives, actions, and anticipated outcomes, allowing for meaningful interaction and knowledge sharing.

Table 19. Attended events

Partner	Type of event	Title of the event	Date	Location
Galway	Event	Food Vision 2030 - A World Leader in Sustainable Food Systems	01/02/2023	Galway, Ireland

Galway	Meeting	The 2nd Meeting of the 6th Mandate of SCAR AKIS	12/04/2023 - 13/04/2023	Prague, Czech Republic
Galway	Forum	The European Startup Village Forum	28/02/2023	Brussels, Belgium
LNU	Conference	Rural Pact Conference	04/05/2023	Uppsala, Sweden
Galway	Event	President of Ireland's Summer Garden Party	21/06/2023	Galway, Ireland
Galway/CE	Event	Tools4CAP first Info Session	26/06/2023	Online

6. CONCLUSIONS

The FLIARA project's Plan for dissemination and exploitation, encompassing communication activities in its initial version, presents a comprehensive and strategic approach to raise awareness and promote the project's objectives. The plan outlines various channels to promote the project, including print and digital media, social media platforms, and different methods for disseminating the project, for example engaging target groups through both online and offline activities, over the first 18 months of the project.

One of the primary goals of the plan is to inform the public about this European Commission-funded initiative and its mission to advance female-led innovations in agriculture and rural areas across the European Union. The approach intends to instil trust and promote collaboration among stakeholders by efficiently communicating information about consortium members and the overall objective of the project. Furthermore, it seeks to create opportunities for active participation from end users and interested parties, facilitating their engagement, collaboration and involvement.

To ensure a consistent and recognisable public image for the project, various communication tools such as leaflets, banners, and roll-ups have been designed, contributing to a cohesive visual identity, and reinforcing the project's message. The plan also incorporates a comprehensive set of monitoring and evaluation indicators to assess the effectiveness of the dissemination and communication efforts, enabling continuous improvement and adaptation as needed.

An essential aspect of the plan is the establishment of partnerships with complementary projects and initiatives. The FLIARA project intends to use collective expertise and resources by connecting with like-minded endeavours, facilitating collaboration and knowledge sharing. This approach maximises the impact and sustainability of the project's outcomes, facilitates the successful dissemination and exploitation of project results while also enhancing the visibility of female-led innovations in the agricultural and rural areas.

ANNEXES

ANNEX 1 – CONSORTIUM GUIDELINES FOR SOCIAL MEDIA

Nowadays, being active on social media is essential. Social media will play an active role in achieving dissemination and communication aims. Please follow the steps outlined in this brief tutorial to achieve effectiveness while sharing key information with stakeholders/followers in a general way.

WHO MANAGES THE PUBLICATIONS?

CE will handle publications on the project's social media accounts. Please communicate every important activity or event that can be shared on every platform by emailing socialmedia@fliara.eu.

Every time you have news, or you have found relevant information that relates to the project, please inform CE so that we can post it. We will post your ideas as well throughout the project. You will find on TEAMS as well an Excel File to fill out with publications (papers, scientific publications, articles, radio/tv interviews) you have done.

FOLLOW AND INVITE TO FOLLOW

Please follow all project accounts, invite your friends and networks on Social Media to give a like on FLIARA Facebook page, connect/follow on LinkedIn and follow on Instagram and Twitter.

- Facebook: /fliara.project
- Instagram: /fliara.project
- Twitter: /fliara_project
- LinkedIn: /fliara-project

RELATED HASHTAGS

Hashtags are a way to disseminate information on most social media platforms. Please consider the following hashtags to convey the message of the project to a wide audience:

#WomenInAg	#FLIARA
#WomenInspiringWomen	#FLIARAEU
#GenderInEquality	#CommunityOfPractice
#RuralInnovation	#Women
#RuralWomen	#GenderEquality

#RuralCommunity	#FemaleLed
#Sustainability	#RuralWomen
#HorizonEU	#Innovation
#Enviroment	#WomenLedInnovation

WHEN ATTENDING EVENTS

Dissemination WP will be monitoring attended events and upcoming events as part of the Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation, including communication activities. Please inform us about every event when FLIARA Project will be participating, and if there is already attended events, let us know as well for reporting purposes. You will find on TEAMS an Excel File to inform us your attended events and upcoming events you would like to participate.

ABOUT CONTENT

When there is something to show to stakeholders and when you are attending events. Please, consider recording videos to post on Stories (Facebook and Instagram), Moments (Twitter), LinkedIn Stories. It will create a visual narrative of all the activities related to the project.

IDEAS OF CONTENT

Here is a list of examples of what you can share with WP6 leader:

- Personal experiences - anything you do as part of the project that surprised you.
- General information - a publication that contains pertinent information on the project's topic.
- Quotations - a phrase that you heard at a conference or read in a publication that you found inspirational and relevant to the project theme.
- A funny fact - this might lend a little of levity to the situation.
- Link to a relevant website with a brief description.
- The project results, newspapers and publications, events, conferences, breaking news, and other hashtags related to our project that you may found interesting.

If partners would like to share a message on social media: write only two or three sentences and include a good photograph. Members of the consortium can hazard writing a long narrative if you wish, but it must be a true story that captures the reader's interest, not just a long message.

ANNEX 3 – SOCIAL MEDIA NETWORKS FROM PARTNERS

Table 21. Social Media Networks from Partners

Short name	Twitter	Instagram	Facebook	LinkedIn	Others
Galway	twitter.com/UniGalwayRural		https://www.facebook.com/universityofgalwayruralstudies/	-	YouTube Channel: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC6deHbBiRcWvuYdNaFrFaaw
TU Delft	@BKTUDelft	https://www.instagram.com/bk.tudelft/	https://www.facebook.com/BKTUDelft	https://www.linkedin.com/company/bktudelft	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCY-kUhbrVu6akhkj9T7Y6A?
Teagasc	-	instagram.com/teagasc	https://www.facebook.com/Teagasc	-	-
UNICAL	-	instagram.com/unical_official	-	-	-
LWL	twitter.com/LWLLongford		www.facebook.com/LongfordWomensLink	www.linkedin.com/in/teefarrell www.linkedin.com/in/lwl-longford-97034ba1	@lwllongford3468
UTU	-	instagram.com/uniturku	-	-	-
UL	twitter.com/FFLjubljana	instagram.com/geoffuni	https://www.facebook.com/geofful	https://www.linkedin.com/school/university-of-ljubljana-arts	YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/@oddelezageografijofful9337
CE	twitter.com/ConsultaEuropa	instagram.com/consulta_europa	https://www.facebook.com/ConsultaEuropa	https://es.linkedin.com/company/consulta-europa?original_referer=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.google.com%2F	-
HNEE	twitter.com/hneeberswalde ;	instagram.com	https://www.facebook.com/hneeberswalde/	https://www.linkedin.com/school/hneeberswalde/	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hBo3XgseqMU

	@Frvmue nchhause n; @liaison2 020	m/hneebersw alde			
ELAR D			https://www.facebo ok.com/ELARDaisb /		http://elard.eu/
UOUL U	twitter.co m/OuluAr chAnth	instagram.co m/oulu.archa eology.anthr opology	-	-	https://www.youtube. com/user/University OfOulu
HLK	twitter.co m/Jonkopi ngUni		https://www.facebo ok.com/hlk.jonkopin g	https://www.link edin.com/compa ny/h-gskolan-f-r- l-rande-och- kommunikation/ ?viewAsMember =true	-
ECOLI SE	twitter.co m/ECOLI SE		https://www.facebo ok.com/ecolise.eu	https://www.link edin.com/compa ny/ecolise/	-
MEND ELU	twitter.co m/MEND ELUcz	https://www.i nstagram.co m/mendelu.c z/?hl=cs	https://www.facebo ok.com/mendelova. univerzita/	https://cz.linkedin .com/school/m endeluniversityi nbrno/	YouTube Channel: https://www.youtube. com/c/mendeluniv
LNU	@linneuni	https://instagr am.com/linne universitetet/	https://www.facebo ok.com/linneunivers itetet?fref=ts	https://www.link edin.com/school /linnaeus- university/	-

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